

IN-SITU X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY CHARACTERISATION OF TENSILE DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN TEXTILE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

Hailong Liu¹, Daxu Zhang^{1*}, Lingyu Zheng¹, Heyin Qi¹, Xiaoyan Wang²

¹School of Naval Architecture, Ocean and Civil Engineering, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China;

²School of Computer Science and Information Engineering, Shanghai Institute of Technology, Shanghai, China

* Corresponding author (daxu.zhang@sjtu.edu.cn)

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ABSTRACT

Tensile damage evolution of plain weave ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) was studied by the in-situ nanofocus X-ray computed tomography (CT) experiment. High resolution three dimensional (3D) CT images of the materials under different tensile loading levels were obtained. The mesoscopic structure of the material, various damage modes and their developments were observed by comparing the CT images of the in-situ tests under different loading levels. Propagation of transverse matrix cracking during loading and its close up after failure were well captured. The progressive damage mechanisms of the material under tension were established.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) are high temperature thermal structural materials known for their high specific strength, high specific modulus, and properties of corrosion resistance, wear resistance, high fracture toughness and thermal stability. Since silicon carbide (SiC) fibers' antioxidant ability under high temperature is superior to carbon fiber, the fiber and matrix have similar thermal expansion coefficient in SiC/SiC ceramic matrix composites whose residual strains are small while working stability are remain stable at 1200 °C, and are expected to be operated at 1650 °C. They are regarded as the favourite material to replace the superalloy and realise the renewal for engine weight reduction and efficiency improvement. In the past two decades, great efforts have been paid to investigate the mechanical behaviour of ceramic matrix composites [1-21].

The microstructure and porosities inside SiC/SiC ceramic matrix composites have a great influence on material strength. X-ray and CT scanning technology, used for accurately detecting the internal microscopic morphology of materials, are currently one of the most effective ways for studying the damage evolution of materials. Besides, the shape, size, width, location and direction of all crack damages can be obtained by CT reconstruction image. The evolution process of these damages determines the nonlinear mechanical behavior of the material and is a true reflection of material damage.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Test Specimen

The test specimens are made of plain weave SiC/SiC composites and they are fabricated by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) process. The image and geometry of an in-situ X-ray CT tensile test specimen are shown in Figure 1. Its thickness is approximately 2.0 mm.

Fig 1 : Geometry and dimensions of the specimen

2.2 In-situ X-ray CT tensile test

To perform in-situ tests within a laboratory nanofocus X-ray CT, a novel mini-loading instrument was developed. Figure 2(b) shows the photograph of the instrument with a CMC specimen installed. The instrument can apply a maximum tensile force of 3 kN with a microstep size of 0.5 μm . Figure 2(c) shows the photo of the in-situ test in operation, where the mini-loading instrument was mounted onto a precision rotation unit. It rotates the instrument and the specimen 360° to finish one scan. During each scan, the displacement-controlled loading stops while the load cell keeps recording the force.

Figure 2: Photograph of the in-situ X-ray CT tensile test. (a) a CMC specimen; (b) the in-situ mini-loading instrument; (c) the setup of an in-situ X-ray CT tensile test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress-strain curve

The tensile stress-strain response of the specimen reflects its internal damage evolution. The tensile stress-strain curve of an in-situ test is plotted in Figure 3. A number of CT scans were carried out and the images obtained at the stress levels of the four red dots marked on the stress-strain curve are representative and will be discussed.

The curve exhibits an obvious nonlinear characteristic and could be roughly divided into three stages. At Stage I (0-0.10), the slope of the curve is linear, indicating that no damage occurred at this range. At Stage II (0.10-0.60), the curve becomes nonlinear and its slope decreases gradually,

implying that material damage initiated and developed. At Stage III (0.60-1.0), the modulus of elasticity is approximately zero, indicating that the material's damage is severe.

Figure 3: Normalised tensile stress-strain curve of a CMC specimen obtained by the in-situ X-ray CT test.

3.2 The microscopic structure of the material

The mesostructure of CMCs and the damage evolution of the specimen under tension was investigated by examining the 3D reconstructed images of the raw CT data. The voxel size of these CT reconstructed images is approximately 5.5 μm when the X-ray tube is closest to the instrument glass tube.

Figure 4: The mesostructure of CMCs

Figure 4 shows the mesostructure of material. Under the influence of the CVI preparation process, the fiber bundle inside the material is not very regular, and there are a large number of initial defects. The initial defects can be classified into small voids and large voids according to their volumes and locations. Small voids are normally contained within a tow, and they comprise either a group of voids or large cracks between the fibres. Large voids are at the intersection of four orthogonal tows and account for the vast majority of defects. Initial defects have an important influence on the matrix cracking of the material.

3.3 Damage evolution

Figure 5 shows the damage development on an internal slice which is located at the dotted line in Figure 4. No damage can be found at low stress levels (Marks 1 and 2). A long transverse matrix crack took place on the crossover edge of warp and weft tows at high stress level (Mark 3). The same crack became longer and wider even after the specimen ruptured and the load dropped to zero (Mark 4). Other damage modes, including longitudinal matrix cracking, delamination, fibre ruptures and close of micro cracking were also captured by the CT images. Matrix cracking is more likely to occur near the voids and at the fiber tows' boundary.

Figure 5: Evolution of damage at an Section

3.4 Fracture analysis

Figure 6 is a scanned image of a section of the test piece after fracture, and it can be found that the warp fiber bundle is almost completely broken at the fracture. The location of the damage is mainly concentrated on the fiber lap joint, the fracture is uneven, and obvious fiber pull-out and interlayer cracking occur. Due to severe delamination, matrix separates from the two adjacent fiber bundles. In the vicinity of the material's faces, damage is more severe than that at the far field.

Figure 6: CT image near the fracture surface of the test specimen

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents an in-situ experimental study on the tensile damage evolution of plain weave CMCs using X-ray CT. The following conclusions can be drawn.

- (1) In-situ nanofocus X-ray CT tests are very effective to study damage modes and their evolution of CMCs.
- (2) No damage can be found at low stress levels when the stress-strain response is linear elastic.
- (3) Transverse matrix cracking takes place at medium and high stress levels when the stress-strain response is nonlinear.
- (4) Fibre pullout and close up of micro transverse cracking were observed after the catastrophic failure of material's ruptures.

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